

TOURIST'S EXPECTATION AND SATISFACTION TOWARDS AMENITIES IN UDHAGAMANDALAM

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Abstract:

Tourism is the travel for recreation, leisure, religious, family and business purposes, usually of a limited duration. Tourism is now one of the world's largest industries and one of its fastest growing economic sectors. For many countries tourism is seen as a main instrument for regional development as it stimulates new economic activities. Tourism is one of the most profitable industries in service sector in India. It contributes more on countries GDP and provides employment opportunity especially to local people who depend on tourism. Tamil Nadu remains an all-season destination for tourists. Udhagamandalam often called as Ooty is the Queen of Hill Stations in India. Ooty offers the visitor an unending array of walks and heights to conquer, not to mention the scenic beauty to be enjoyed in the most pleasant of climate. Every year tourists arrivals to Ooty shows increasing trend. The tourists need some basic facilities like water, medical, transport, etc., for their enjoyment of tour to Ooty. Governments take necessary steps for providing various basic facilities to tourists. Therefore this study focuses its direction on tourists' expectation and satisfaction towards amenities in Ooty.

Key Words: Tourism, Amenities, Ooty, Expectation & Satisfaction

Introduction:

Travel and tourism have been important social activities of human beings. The urge to explore new places within one's own country or outside and seek a change of environment has been experienced from ancient times. Throughout the course of history, people have travelled for purposes of trade, religious conviction, economic gain, war, migration and other equally compelling motivators. Tourism has become an essential factor for all round development. It earns money and enriches foreign exchange. It creates job opportunities and thus alleviates poverty. Tourism industry occupies an important place in the world's economy. Tamil Nadu remains an all-season destination for tourists – backpackers heading for the beaches, the city-bred searching for that rural experience, the devout seeking spiritual solace in myriad temples, the ones bound for hill stations to escape the blazing sun, or those arriving for treatment.

Ooty- Queen of Hill Station:

Udhagamandalam popularly called, as Ooty is the Queen of Hill Stations in India. Udhagamandalam is the capital of the Nilgiris district. The Nilgiris Hill forms a part of the Western Ghats. The name Nilgiris was due to by the blue haze envelops the range with most distant hills of considerable size. Doddabetta, the highest peak in South India with an altitude of 2,595 Meters lies in this District. The other prominent hills of this District are Elk hills, Devarshola peak, Hulical hill and Cairn hill. The main tourist attraction in this District is the Botanical Garden. Besides the Botanical Garden there are several other places. The important among them are the boat house near Bus-stand, the Rose Garden, the Deer Park, and the Doddabetta peak in Udhagamandalam. Sim's park, Pasture Institute, Kateri falls, Lamb's rock and Dolphin's nose are the Important Tourist sports in Coonoor. In Kotagiri block Kodanadu view point and St. Catherine's falls are the two main tourist attractions. In Gudalur block the main tourist attraction in Mudumalai wild Life Sanctuary.

Statement of the Problem:

Today the important of tourism on national economy becomes increasingly important because of the growing size of the tourist market. From the economic angle tourism is especially important in a developing country like India. Customer satisfaction is the key to survival in today's stiff competition of any industry in the world. Tourism usually offers both tangible and intangible experiences to their customers which are complementary each other and perceived as the integral parts of a whole travel experience. Although the tangible and intangible products are dissimilar in characteristics, they can be distinguished by their effects on customer satisfaction or combined for improving customer satisfaction.

Ooty (Udhagamandalam) is a hilly place in Tamilnadu, which attracts many domestic and international tourists. The natural diversity of Ooty Such as natural attractions, climate and weather conditions, scenic beauty, sightseeing, flora and fauna, varieties of flowers and trees are important to attract more tourists during the seasonal and non seasonal periods. It arrtracts domestic as well as foreign tourists. Improvement in transport and communication facilities leads to travel to Ooty. The tourists need some basic facilities like water, medical,

transport, etc., for their enjoyment of tour to Ooty. Both Government and private service providers offer such facilities to the tourists. This induces the researcher to study about tourists' expectation and satisfaction towards amenities in Ooty.

Objectives of the Study:

- The main objectives of the study are,
- ✓ To study about the socio economic profile of the tourists.
 - ✓ To analyze the tourist's expectation towards amenities in Ooty.
 - ✓ To measure the tourist's satisfaction towards amenities in Ooty.

Scope and Significance of the Study:

The study has been undertaken from the point of view of the tourist who is visited to Ooty. The present study aims to identify the tourists' Expectation and satisfaction towards Amenities such as Drinking water, Banking Facilities, Medical, and Transport etc., which are available in Ooty. The result of the study may be useful for the Government, in order to improve basic facilities in Ooty such a way that to attract more number of tourists and their further visit.

Research Design:

Research design briefly gives details about the method of data collection, pilot study and analysis of data. This study is descriptive in nature. The methodology of the present study is outlined here under.

Population - Population for selecting sample units of the study includes tourist both Domestic and International tourist who visit Ooty.

Period of Study - The research work was carried out for the period of 1year starting from June 2015 to May 2016.

Sampling Technique - In this study purposive random sampling technique is used to select the sample.

Sample Size - In this study, the researcher took 400 samples from the population.

Pilot Study- Before starting the main study, a sample of 50 tourists in Ooty were randomly selected and surveyed. The outcomes of the pilot study were quite encouraging.

Source and Tool for Data Collection - In this study both primary and secondary data were used. The primary data is collected through a well structured questionnaire. The secondary data were collected from Magazines, Books, Journals, Tourism office, Government Reports and Statistics, websites etc.,

Tools for Analysis - The various statistical tools used in this study are simple percentage analysis, Standard Deviation, weighted average and Factor analysis.

Limitations of the Study:

- The limitations of this study are,
- ✓ The study is confined to Ooty only.
 - ✓ The analysis was made based on the information provided by the respondents; their opinions are dynamics they keep changing time to time.

Review of Literature:

Jacob Konwar & Deb Kr. Chakraborty (2015), pointed out that there is a significant mean difference in the opinions of the domestic and foreign visitors regarding the tourism related products and services Elangovan and Govindan (2013), in their study they concluded that improvement of various infrastructure facilities, parking facilities, road connectivity, medical facilities, shopping facilities, drinking water facilities etc., in Ooty brings more tourists from the different part of India and rest of the world in future.

Shobha K (2012) pointed out that Tourism has found a niche for itself as an effective instrument for generating employment, earning revenue and foreign exchange, enhancing environment, preserving culture and traditional thereby facilitating overall development. To improve the volume of tourism in Ooty, infrastructural facilities have to be improved. Renushree H K and Uma H R (2011), in their study they recommended that along with existing, additional signage and brochures at that path way to every tourist's or their group in order to make them eco conscious in urgently needed.

Babu S (2010), stated that there is a need for further improvement of basic infrastructure in order to attract tourists and also providing detailed information about the tourists spot on the Internet as most tourists seem to access the web to identify the ideal destination for their visits. Xavier S (2010), found that most of the respondents were satisfied with the facilities such as Water, Boarding and Lodging, Guide services etc., which are provided in the tourist spots of Tamilnadu.

Mohinder Chand (2010) applies the SERVQUAL measurement instrument to evaluate the tourism services at ten Indian tourist destinations visited by foreign tourists and provide evidence of where specific service improvements were needed to enhance the competitiveness of the destination(s). Perunjodi Naidoo, et. al. (2010) rightly highlighted that tourist satisfaction is one of the most investigated topics in the field of tourism due to its role in the survival of a destination.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

The results of the analysis of the collected Data are presented below:

Table 1: Socio-Economic Profile of the Respondents

Socio – Economic Factors		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	184	46%
	Female	216	54%
Age	18-20	70	18%
	21-25	94	24%
	26-30	86	22%
	31-35	44	11%
	36-40	80	20%
	Above 40	26	7%
Marital Status	Unmarried	152	38%
	Married	220	55%
	Separated	20	5%
	Widow	08	2%
Educational Qualification	Up to SSLC	24	6%
	HSC	74	19%
	Graduation	214	54%
	Diploma	46	12%
	Others	42	11%
Employment Status	Homemaker	34	9%
	Service	60	15%
	Own business	126	32%
	Professional	118	30%
	Others	62	16%
Monthly Income	Below Rs.10000	22	6%
	Rs.10001 To Rs. 25000	90	23%
	Rs. 25001to Rs. 50000	130	33%
	Above Rs. 50001	158	40%
Family Size	Up To 2	80	20%
	3-4	202	51%
	5 to 6	84	21%
	Above 6	34	9%
Nationality	Indian	296	74%
	Foreign National	104	26%
Place of Origin	Within Tamil Nadu	182	46%
	Other States of India	96	24%
	Union Territory	26	7%
	European	24	6%
	American	34	9%
	Australian	22	6%
	Asian countries	10	3%
	African	6	2%

Source: Primary Data

The above table reveals the socio –Economic Profile of the respondents. From this it should be clear that Females are highly interested to visit Ooty, the respondents who are belonging to the age group of 21-25 are highly make a travel to Ooty, majority of 55% of the respondents are married, majority of 54% of the respondents are Graduate, respondents who make a travel to Ooty are mostly doing own Business, most of the respondents have a monthly income of above Rs. 50,001, majority of the respondents family have 3-4 members, majority of 74% of the respondents are Indian and most of the tourists who resides in Tamilnadu are highly involved in tour to Ooty.

Expectation towards Amenities:

Expectation is differ according to the age, gender, income level, etc., Therefore tourists Expectation towards amenities are analyzed and classified as highly expect, somewhat expect, Neither Expect nor not expect, not expect and highly not expect.

Table 2: Tourists' Expectation towards Amenities

	Expectation Level											
	Highly Expect		Somewhat Expect		Neither Expect Nor Not Expect		Not Expect		Highly Not Expect		Total	
Drinking water	290	73	99	25	11	3					400	100
Transport	175	44	168	42	54	14	3	.8			400	100
Commercial tourist Attraction	160	40	119	30	102	26	19	5			400	100
Campsites	140	35	141	35	89	22	25	6	5	1	400	100
Communication	131	33	153	38	93	23	11	3	12	3	400	100
Banking	158	40	73	18	152	38	9	2	8	2	400	100
Insurance	142	36	108	27	119	30	28	7	3	.8	400	100
Medical	177	44	134	34	80	20	6	2	3	.8	400	100
Emergency Services	177	44	112	28	95	24	16	4			400	100
Security Services	148	37	138	35	93	23	16	4	5	1.	400	100
Sporting and recreation	146	36	103	26	110	28	36	9	5	1.	400	100
Information Centres and Guide Services	143	35	108	27	116	29	31	8	2	.5	400	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above Table 2, it should be clear that Tourists are highly expected towards Drinking water facilities followed by medical, emergency services, transport, commercial tourist attraction, banking services, Security services, Sporting and recreation, Information Centers and Guide Services, Insurance, Campsites and Communication.

Satisfaction towards Amenities:

The satisfactions towards amenities are listed in the following table.

Table 3: Tourists' Satisfaction towards Amenities

Source: Primary Data

From the above Table 3, it should be clear that Tourists are highly dissatisfied towards Drinking water facilities followed by commercial tourist attraction, transport, Security services, medical, banking services, Campsites, Information Centers and Guide Services, Communication, Insurance, emergency services and Sporting and recreation.

Factor Analysis on Expectation towards Amenities:

The results of the fitness test regarding factor analysis based on inter correlation matrix has been presented in the following Table.

Table 4: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.722
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	972.151
	Df	66
	Sig.	0.000

Source: Computed from Primary Data

The above table clears that the KMO Value is 0.722 which is not less than 0.5 and hence satisfactory. So, the factor analysis for the present study is effective and suitable. In the present study, the data matrix comprising of a large number of identified variables which are inter- related have been tested and the same has been presented below.

Table 5: Communalities

Amenities	Initial	Extraction
Drinking water	1.000	0.604
Transport	1.000	0.519
Commercial tourist Attraction	1.000	0.656
Campsites	1.000	0.647
Communication	1.000	0.511
Banking	1.000	0.462
Insurance	1.000	0.501

Medical	1.000	0.679
Emergency Services	1.000	0.697
Security Services	1.000	0.668
Sporting and Recreation	1.000	0.568
Information centres and Guide services	1.000	0.668

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

The above table 5 indicates that, the extracted communalities are high and acceptable for all the variables.

Table 6: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.32	27.62	27.62	3.32	27.62	27.62	2.25	18.71	18.71
2	1.54	12.86	40.48	1.54	12.86	40.48	1.86	15.49	34.19
3	1.31	10.90	51.38	1.31	10.90	51.38	1.62	13.49	47.68
4	1.01	8.45	59.83	1.01	8.45	59.83	1.46	12.15	59.83
5	0.90	7.52	67.35						
6	0.75	6.24	73.59						
7	0.70	5.83	79.42						
8	0.65	5.38	84.80						
9	0.56	4.67	89.47						
10	0.48	3.96	93.43						
11	0.43	3.60	97.03						
12	0.36	2.97	100						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

The above table shows that though there are 12 variables that can be extracted, only 4 variables can be extracted among the 12 variables which have Eigen value more than one. Of which it is inferred that 27.62 percent of variance is explained by variable one, 12.86 percent of variance is explained by variable two, 10.90 percent of variance is explained by variable three and 8.45 percent of variance is explained by variable four.

Extraction sum of squared loadings is also used for measuring the level of expectation towards amenities in Ooty. It indicates that the total of 59.83 percent variance is not uniformly distributed across all the variables. Since it is evident that, the first variable accounts for 27.62 percent variance, second variables accounts for 12.86 percent variance and third variable accounts for 10.90 percent variance. As the variance are not uniformly distributed, the rotated sum of squared loadings method is used to distribute the variables uniformly across all the factors whose Eigen value is more than one. Variables rotation (Rotated Component Matrix) was applied for all the 12 variables and presented below.

Table 7: Rotated Component Matrix^a

Amenities	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Drinking water	-0.68	.105	.133	.755
Transport	.230	.062	.310	.605
Commercial tourist Attraction	.144	.129	.773	.144
Campsites	.190	.046	.768	.136
Communication	.643	-.018	.310	.034
Banking	.499	.412	.201	.050
Insurance	.553	.282	-.075	.332
Medical	.054	.707	-.159	.389
Emergency Services	-.010	.815	.155	.095
Security Services	.227	.625	.253	-.402
Sporting and Recreation	.671	.129	.246	-.202
Information centres and Guide services	.811	-.065	.028	.075

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Rotation converged in 6 iterations.

Factor Analysis on Satisfaction towards Amenities:

The results of the fitness test regarding factor analysis based on inter correlation matrix has been presented in the following Table.

Table 8: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.795
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	955.745
	Df	66
	Sig.	0.000

Source: Computed from Primary Data

The above table clears that the KMO Value is **0.795** which is not less than 0.5 and hence satisfactory. So, the factor analysis for the present study is effective and suitable. In the present study, the data matrix comprising of a large number of identified variables which are inter-related have been tested and the same has been presented below.

Table 9: Communalities

Amenities	Initial	Extraction
Drinking water	1.000	.557
Transport	1.000	.705
Commercial tourist Attraction	1.000	.544
Campsites	1.000	.562
Communication	1.000	.506
Banking	1.000	.693
Insurance	1.000	.543
medical	1.000	.668
Emergency Services	1.000	.532
Security Services	1.000	.519
Sporting and recreation	1.000	.536
Information centres and Guide services	1.000	.762

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

The above table 9, indicates that, the extracted communalities are high and acceptable for all the variables.

Table 10: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.60	30.01	30.01	3.60	30.01	30.01	1.98	16.52	16.52
2	1.34	11.15	41.16	1.34	11.15	41.16	1.88	15.64	32.17
3	1.13	9.43	50.59	1.13	9.43	50.59	1.75	14.59	46.76
4	1.06	8.80	59.39	1.06	8.80	59.39	1.52	12.63	59.39
5	0.83	6.93	66.32						
6	0.70	5.85	72.17						
7	0.67	5.62	77.79						
8	0.66	5.46	83.24						
9	0.60	5.03	88.28						
10	0.57	4.77	93.05						
11	0.46	3.80	96.85						
12	0.38	3.15	100						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

The above table shows that though there are 12 variables that can be extracted, only 4 variables can be extracted among the 12 variables which have Eigen value more than one. Of which it is inferred that 30.01 percent of variance is explained by variable one, 11.15 percent of variance is explained by variable two, 9.43 percent of variance is explained by variable three and 8.80 percent of variance is explained by variable four.

Extraction sum of squared loadings is also used for measuring the level of expectation towards amenities in Ooty. It indicates that the total of 59.39 percent variance is not uniformly distributed across all the variables. Since it is evident that, the first variable accounts for 30.01 percent variance, second variables accounts for 11.15 percent variance and third variable accounts for 9.43 percent variance. As the variance are not uniformly distributed, the rotated sum of squared loadings method is used to distribute the variables uniformly across all the factors whose Eigen value is more than one. Variables rotation (Rotated Component Matrix) was applied for all the 12 variables and presented below.

Table 11: Rotated Component Matrix^a

Amenities	Component			
	1	2	3	4

Drinking water	.676	.014	.297	.110
Transport	.562	.590	-.197	.049
Commercial tourist Attraction	.726	.079	.058	.086
Campsites	.668	.312	.057	.124
Communication	.157	.493	.213	.439
Banking	.062	.804	.112	.172
Insurance	.197	.623	.321	-.116
medical	.327	-.090	.743	.028
Emergency Services	.024	.285	.670	.031
Security Services	-.013	.180	.630	.299
Sporting and recreation	.246	.156	.241	.626
Information centres and Guide services	.043	-.021	-.009	.872

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Rotation converged in 6 iterations.

Findings of the Study:

The present study reveals that

- ✓ Among the 400 tourists, 54% of them are female and 46% are male.
- ✓ 24% of the tourists are belonging to the age group of 21 – 25 years next by 22% of the tourists are in the age group of 26-30 years.
- ✓ Majority (55%) of the tourists are married.
- ✓ Among the tourists respondents majority (54%) of the respondents are Graduate.
- ✓ 32% of the respondents are having own business and 30% of the respondents are professionals.
- ✓ Among the respondents, 40% are belong to monthly income of above Rs.50001 followed by monthly income of Rs.25001 – Rs. 50,000
- ✓ Majority of 51% of the respondent's family size is 3-4 members' which stands first and next is of 5 to 6 persons.
- ✓ 74% of the respondents are Indians and rests are foreign tourists.
- ✓ 46% of the respondents are come from Tamil Nadu followed by 24% are come from other states, 7% are come from union territories in India and rest are from Foreign countries.
- ✓ In case of Drinking Water facility, totally 63% of the respondents are satisfied, of which 30% are having higher level satisfaction.
- ✓ 37% of the respondents are totally satisfied with Transport facility which was provided by both Public and private, out of which 14% are having higher level satisfaction.
- ✓ 45% of the respondents are totally satisfied with Commercial tourist attractions, of which 19% are having higher level satisfaction.
- ✓ In case of Campsites 32% of the respondents are totally satisfied, of which 12% are having high level satisfaction.
- ✓ In Communication services 40% of the respondents are totally satisfied, of which 11% are having high level satisfaction.
- ✓ 36% of the respondents are totally satisfied with banking services which was offered by both Public and private, out of which 12% are having high level satisfaction.
- ✓ 39% of the respondents are totally satisfied towards Insurance services, of which 11% are having high level satisfaction.
- ✓ In case of Medical facilities 38% of the respondents are totally satisfied. of which 13% are having higher level satisfaction.
- ✓ 39% of the respondents are totally satisfied with emergency services, of which 9% are having high level satisfaction.
- ✓ In case of Security services, totally 38% of the respondents are satisfied. of which 14% are having high level satisfaction.
- ✓ 28% of the respondents are totally satisfied with Sporting and recreation, out of which 9% are having high level satisfaction
- ✓ 32% of the respondents are totally satisfied with Information centres and Guide services, of which 12% are having high level satisfaction.

Suggestions:

The following suggestions should be given for the improvement of tourism in Ooty.

- ✓ Cleanliness, hygienic conditions and satisfactory catering should exist at every place of tourist interest.
- ✓ Take necessary steps for providing adequate parking space facility and supply of pure drinking water.
- ✓ Efforts to be taken for providing adequate number of clean toilet facilities.

- ✓ Mode of Transportation through Airways, Roadways and Train to be Oriented. Such Co-ordination will definitely help the tourists.
- ✓ Government will create basic infrastructure for tourism development and also act as a facilitator for private investment in this sector.

Conclusion:

From the above analysis it's concluded that the economy of Ooty is predominately run by Tourism. The local people are largely depends on tourism for their survival. If tourist arrivals are increased, it will leads to higher standard of living. Tourists are having higher level expectation towards amenities. Even though the conscious effort was taken for providing basic amenities to tourist still there may be a gap between their expectation and satisfaction. Tourists are highly satisfied with necessary facilities like drinking water, transport, medical etc., when it should be provided in regular, adequate and hygienic manner. Therefore the Government must concentrate on improvement of such facilities, if do so definitely it will boost the tourism industry in Ooty and survival of local people.

Scope for Further Research:

- ✓ This Study Focus Only on Ooty, hence it may be extended to other similar tourist destination in Tamil Nadu as well as in India.
- ✓ An analysis may be made in order to found out tourist satisfaction towards various services which are marketed in tourist place by marketers.
- ✓ A comparative analysis of two or more tourist destination is possible if they are in same kind.
- ✓ The study may be extended to find out the gap between tourists expectation and satisfaction towards amenities and any other services.

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